

BIO-INSPIRED REVERSIBLE CROSSLINKING, USING CHELATING POLYMERS AND METAL ION BINDING, FOR USE AS SOFT ACTUATION AND SELECTIVE GROWTH

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ABSTRACT

Ionoprinting, a technique used to pattern hydrogels with metal cations, has been used to create hydrogel actuation. The technique prints metal cations into the surface and near surface of a hydrogel creating localised ionic crosslinking and contraction, resulting in rapid structural morphing of the hydrogel. A synthetic acrylate based hydrogel has been developed that contains 20 mol% phosphate functionalised side groups; the phosphate functional group is found in many protein based underwater adhesives utilising polypeptide metal cation bonding to promote "wet" adhesion.

The crosslinking strength of varies metal cations with this phosphate containing hydrogel have been determined, with vanadium(III) and (IV), iron(III), manganese(II) and calcium(II) cations all significantly contracting the hydrogel. The magnitude of the ionic crosslinking is ion concentration dependent, with an increase in concentration causing increasing crosslinking and decreasing swelling, until system saturation is reach. The global swelling of the hydrogel can be controlled by solvent immersion. It was observed that the polarity of the solvent had a direct linear relationship to the magnitude of the swelling, i.e. the greater the polarity of the solvent the greater the swelling.

In our study, Ionoprinting has been used to create 3D polygons and origami shapes from flat hydrogels; we have created a morphing triangular based pyramid, a cube, an octahedron and an "umbrella". The printed 3D shapes can be unfolded in one of two ways; either the immersion of the hydrogel into a less polar solvent, retaining the ionoprinted lines, or immersion in a solution of chelating agent thus removing the ionoprinted lines. The unfolded polygon can be refolded again by placement into a more polar solvent or through re-ionoprinting again, respectively. Ionoprinting offers a simple and effective way of creating morphing shape-changing hydrogels, a process that is both reversible and reprogrammable.

1 INTRODUCTION

Hydrogels consist of three-dimensional hydrophilic polymer chains crosslinked together to create a polymer network that swells in water but does not dissolve; creating a material that lies between a solid and a liquid, namely a gel. The amount of water absorbed by hydrogels can be varied by external stimuli such as pH, temperature or electric field [1]. One of the limitations of hydrogels is also one of their greatest assets, their ability to only act in aqueous media; allowing them to act in biological and wet environments, which are often inaccessible for other actuators [2]. Homogenous hydrogels when submerged into water will ultimately result in homogenous swelling in all directions, inhomogeneous

swelling can be produced by subjecting the hydrogel to an inhomogeneous environment [3]. The most widely used approach to achieve inhomogeneous shape change from homogenous hydrogels is to combine them with other homogenous hydrogels or materials, with the geometry of the material combination controlling the movement and final shape [4]. Another approach is to use ionoprinting, a technique used to print metal cations onto the surface and near surface of hydrogels allowing homogeneous hydrogels to shape change in an inhomogeneous manner by creating local inhomogeneity within the hydrogel. Ionoprinting uses the principles of electrolysis to create localised ionic crosslinking and shrinkage where the cations are deposited, creating a bending hydrogel [5-6].

Biological systems operate in a significantly more limited environment with a reduced range of elements than engineers and scientists, yet Nature is still able to create a vastly diverse range of materials. This work uses inspiration from biological systems to create reversible crosslinking that can operate in aqueous environments. Metal cation-polypeptide crosslinking to create tough and stiff materials has been the inspiration for many biomimetic materials, the one most widely used is the catechol-iron interaction found in mussel byssal threads [7-9]. It has been found that similar binding between phosphate functional groups with calcium and magnesium cations exists within the cement of the sandcastle worm [10-11]. This binding technique has been used to create dental adhesives that are required to work in wet environments [12].

This paper presents a synthetic hydrogel that significantly decreases its water content in the presence of multivalent metals cations through chain-cation-chain crosslinking. Metal cations have been localised to select regions through ionoprinting to create localised multi-chain cation crosslinks resulting in localised deswelling and surface contraction. These hydrogels respond linearly to solvent polarity. This effect has been utilised to create shape changing hydrogels that can be transformed globally from a swollen to a relative deswollen state while having select ionoprinted regions retain their deswollen state throughout global swelling and deswelling. A range of polygon prototypes have been used to demonstrate this effect. While more complex ionoprinting patterns have been used to create hydrogel shape transformations that grow in different directions depending upon environment.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

Materials: Phosphoric acid 2-hydroxyethyl methacrylate ester (PHMA), 2-Hydroxyethyl acrylate (HEA), N,N'-Methylenebisacrylamide (MBAA), 2,2-Dimethoxy-2-phenylacetophenone (DMPA) and triethylamine (TEA) were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (Poole, UK). 2-(methacryloyloxy)ethyl phosphate (MOEP) was extracted from PHMA with n-hexane and HEA was filtered through basic alumina, while DMPA, MBAA and TEA were used without further purification.

Preparation of hydrogels: The monomers (HEA and MOEP) were combined in a molar ratio of 4:1, respectively, before being neutralised with TEA. Crosslinker (MBAA) and photoinitiator (DMPA) were added prior to dissolution with water:DMSO (2:1) resulting a precursor solution with total monomer, crosslinker and photoinitiator of concentration of 2.5M, 12.5mM and 3.0mM respectively. The precursor solution was degassed and then poured into PLA molds and sealed with glass slides prior to curing under a UV lamp (365/245nm, 4W) for 2 hours. Hydrogels were soaked in frequently changed di-ionised water prior to further tested.

Hydrogel swelling: Hydrogels were swollen in 6.0ml of the test solution and allowed to equilibrate over 48 hours. Samples were pat dried with paper towel prior to weighing and were weighed to an accuracy of 0.01g.

Ionoprinting: Hydrogels swollen in 0.1 M LiCl solution, unless otherwise stated, for a minimum of 48 hours were pat dried. Superficially dry samples were ionoprinted between an aluminium foil cathode and a copper, vanadium or iron anode using a Rapid DC Power Supply HY3003C. Current was measured with an iNLEC DT-830B Digital multimeter.

3 RESULTS & DISCUSSION

3.1 Metal chloride crosslinking

It is known that the phosphate functionalised polymers can bind to metal cations, this effect has been used for self-healing, shape-memory and controlled release of enzymes from synthetic hydrogel

[13–15]. In this work the phosphate metal cation interaction is used to create ionic crosslinking of polymer chains; the strength of these crosslinks is determined by de-swelling of synthetic hydrogels in metal chloride solution. The aim for this work was to maximise the hydrogel shrinkage whilst minimising the concentration of metal cation. A range of metal chloride cations were tested from group I, group II and the first row of the transition metals; where the majority of the metals tested were divalent cations.

Figure 1: Bar chart of % of potential swelling of hydrogel in 0.1 M metal chloride solution. Key: ■ Water, ■ Group I, ■ Group II & ■ 1st row transition metal. Error bars ± 1 standard deviation

Figure 1 shows the effect 0.1 M solutions of different metal chlorides has on the hydrogels' potential to swell. All hydrogels deswelled in the presence of the metal chloride solutions. Group I metal chloride showed the least deswelling of all the samples, within Group I a trend can also be seen of the smaller the cation the less deswelling caused. While Group II cations caused more deswelling than Group I, these caused similar deswelling to divalent first row transition metal cations. Divalent first row transition metals showed a trend from right to left across the periodic table of increased deswelling. Tri- and tetravalent cations of first row transition showed more deswelling than mono- and divalent cations with the most promising tested being vanadium(III), which achieved near complete deswelling of the samples, with a final mass near that of the dried sample.

$$\% \text{ swelling compared to water} = (M_s \div M_w) \times 100 \quad (1)$$

M_s is the mass of the sample swollen in the solution under investigation and M_w is the calculated mass of the same sample if swollen in water.

$$M_s = M_d \times SR \quad (2)$$

M_d is the mass of the dried sample and SR is the swelling ratio, which is simply the mass of a sample swollen in water over the mass of the dried sample.

3.2 Metal chloride crosslinking effect of concentration

As well as metal and charge of cations, the concentration of cations was investigated. Copper(II) chloride was chosen to investigate the effect of concentration of swelling of the hydrogel. Copper(II) chloride was chosen for the investigation as at 0.1 M concentration it allowed for both increased or decreased swelling, the copper(II) cation is clearly visible in solutions, and highly concentrated solutions can be prepared. Samples were prepared with initial cured dimensions of 20 mm by 50 mm by 1mm and were then swollen in water and copper(II) chloride of various concentrations (6.0 ml). The swelling of the hydrogel was determined relative to its potential in DI water.

All samples swelled less in copper(II) chloride solution than in water, with the swelling decreasing rapidly until 0.1 M of copper(II) chloride solution where a minimum was achieved, prior to gradual

reswelling up to 4.0 M (see Figure 3). This trend can be explained as initially the copper cations bind to the phosphate groups causing ionic crosslinking, resulting in deswelling, as the concentration of copper cations increases the number of crosslinks increases and the swelling ability decreases until a saturation point is reached where all the phosphates have been crosslinked by the copper cations; beyond this point no further crosslinking will occur and the swelling of the hydrogel will remain constant at a minimum. However, beyond the saturation point of 0.1 M of copper cations a very gradual increase in swelling is seen, a possible cause for this gradual increase could be due to increasing density of copper(II) chloride solution with increasing concentration. The samples are only increased in mass and not in dimensions, this can be seen in Figure 3.

Figure 2: Graph of concentration of copper(II) chloride solution against swelling compared to water. Error bars ± 1 standard deviation. Detail A: 0-0.2 M copper(II) chloride solution

Figure 3: Swelling of cuboid samples in water and copper(II) chloride solutions. Left to right: DI water, 0.005, 0.01, 0.05, 0.1, 0.2, 0.4, 1.0, 2.0 and 4.0 M solutions of copper(II) chloride solution

The saturation point occurs at 0.1 M when samples are swollen to approximately 41% of their water potential. This amount of swelling correlates to a swelling ratio from cured mass to swollen of 1.80 (± 0.06). This swelling from cured results in a dilution of the phosphate group concentration from 0.50 M to 0.28 M, while the addition of the hydrogel to the solution resulted in a dilution from 0.10 M to 0.098 M. Therefore the ratio of phosphate functional groups to copper cations is 1 to 2.80.

3.3 Copper(II) extraction

The extraction of the copper cations from the hydrogels was investigated by diffusion in water and complexation with ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA). Samples that had been previously swollen in copper(II) chloride solutions of strength between 0.1 to 4.0 M and water were pat dried and submerged into water for 2 days. The samples were then swollen in water or 0.1 M disodium EDTA

solutions for a further 3 days. After the first water wash the solutions with concentrations above 0.2 M were all visibly blue in colour with increasing intensity correlating with increasing original concentration. The samples washed purely in water showed no visible colourisation in the bulk of the solution on their second wash; whilst the samples washed in EDTA showed a clearly visible blue colourisation in the bulk of the solution on their second wash. Figure 4 shows the samples after 5 days of washing. The samples washed purely with DI water did not reswell to the size of the water samples achieving an average swelling of 47.16% (2.34% STD) compared to water samples, the photograph clearly shows this difference in swelling and all the remaining blue colourisation indicating the presence of copper(II) cations. While the samples washed in EDTA recovered to 99.83% (5.31% STD) of that of the water samples, with the photographs showing this recovery and the lack of visible blue colourisation indicating that the majority of the copper(II) cations have been removed by the EDTA solution.

Figure 4: From left to right: Photographs of hydrogel swollen in water and 0.1, 0.2, 0.4, 1.0, 2.0 and 4.0 M copper(II) chloride solution and washed in (Top) DI water and (Bottom) 0.1 M Na₂EDTA

3.4 Solvent effect on swelling

The amount a hydrogel swells in water or any other solvent is determined by the Helmholtz free energy of the system. The free energy of a hydrogel can be split into the energy required to stretch the network during swelling and the entropic and enthalpic gains from solvent-gel interactions. These competing driving forces are described by the Gaussian chain model and the Flory–Huggins model, respectively [1]. By decreasing the solvent polarity the entropic and enthalpic gains through solvent-gel interactions are decreased.

Dried hydrogels were submerged into a range of solvents and solvent mixtures of water and water-miscible solvents and allowed to equilibrate before their final weight measured. Potential swelling relative to water was determined as previously described and plotted against solvent polarity.

The relationship between swelling and polarity is linear with increased polarity of solvent causing increased swelling of the hydrogel. This effect can be used to globally swell/deswell the hydrogel or swell the hydrogel to the required level anywhere between “dry” and fully swollen. The solvents investigated were iso-propanol (IPA, 3.90), tetrahydrofuran (THF, 4.00), dioxane (4.80), ethanol (EtOH, 5.20), acetonitrile (5.80), dimethylformamide (DMF, 6.40) and dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO, 7.20). While all the solvents tested are both polar and water soluble, they possess a wide range of functionality which can be broadly split into protic and aprotic. A protic solvent is a polar solvent that

has a liable proton (H^+) attached to either a nitrogen or an oxygen, while conversely an aprotic is unable to donate a hydrogen atom. The protic solvents tested were water, EtOH and IPA all of which possess a liable proton attached to an oxygen i.e. a hydroxyl group, these solvents span a range polarities and show an even stronger linear relationship with $R^2=0.962$. While the aprotic solvents tested are not as simply related as the protic solvents; THF and dioxane can be grouped together as they both are cyclic ethers and achieve their polarity through their ester functional groups, while acetonitrile, DMF and DMSO achieved their polarity through their cyano, amide and sulfoxide groups, respectively. The polar index of these solvents allows them to be compared based on their polarity regardless of its origin.

Figure 5: Graph of hydrogel swelling compared to water in a variety of water miscible solvents and water solvent mixtures plotted against polar index. Linear line of best fit, $R^2=0.8872$

By swelling in different solvents partial dehydration can be achieved throughout the hydrogel and can be used to decrease or segment the deswelling and swelling of hydrogels to prevent self-fraction caused by differential stresses created by air deswelling and full water submersion.

3.5 Ionoprinting

Figure 6: Schematic diagram of ionoprinting of a hydrogel with a copper and aluminium electrode [5]

Ionoprinting is a technique used to selectively pattern metal cations onto the surface/near surface of a hydrogel, the technique was first described by Palleau *et al.* in their paper in 2013 [5]. Their work

described the patterning of poly(acrylic acid) (PAA) with copper cations (Cu^{2+}) to form increased ionic crosslinking, reduction in water concentration and deswelling in the ionoprinted region. Ionoprinting utilises the principals of electrolysis but due to the presence of possible binding sites e.g. carboxylic acid groups, the cations produced do not diffuse rapidly away from the electrode and become bound to these sites. Within Palleau *et al.* it is stated that hydrogen was reduced and the copper was oxidised, these redox processes occurred at the aluminum cathode and the copper anode respectively [5]. Using standard electrode potential it can be determined that E_{cell} is -0.3419V giving the theoretical threshold voltage for ionoprinting [16].

As previously discussed, within this work phosphate groups were used as the binding group for ionoprinting and the binding potential of various metal cations was used to select suitable metals for use as electrodes in the ionoprinting process. The metals chosen were vanadium and iron as both their trivalent cations produced significant deswelling. Their E_{cells} when used to produce hydrogen is 1.430V and 0.037V respectively. An iron electrode has been previously used to ionoprint hydrogels containing catechol functional groups that bound to metal cations [6].

3.6 Variables effecting Ionoprinting

In our study, we have assessed the variables that can affect the cations imprinting into the hydrogel through ionoprinting. In particular, we assessed the voltage, the duration of printing and concentration of lithium chloride that the hydrogels were swollen within prior to printing. Both the final geometry, i.e. 0° flat and 180° fully folded onto itself, and electrons produced were recorded to determine the effectiveness of the ionoprinting technique. All these variables were evaluated employing iron rods with a diameter of 2.8mm on samples of cured size of $1 \times 20 \times 5\text{mm}$, with each experimental condition tested on 5 repetitions.

Figure 7a shows that with increasing ionoprinting duration both the amount of moles of iron cations and angle produced increased. The angle produced ranged from 5 to 170° with shorter ionoprinting producing both a more consistent amount of ions and folding angle produced, this consistency is lost with increasing ionoprinting time. Printing for 5 minutes produced angles between 80 and 170° , and between 1.850 and 3.137×10^{-5} moles of Fe^{3+} ions. While these results show that ionoprinting can produce the full range of angles possible within a relatively short ionoprinting time (relative to hydrogel swelling/deswelling), they do not produce highly repeatable results at longer durations.

The surface wetness of the hydrogel, controlled by pat drying the samples by hand, is thought to have a large effect on the ionoprinting effectiveness. The conductivity of the hydrogel is dependent on the conductivity of the 'swelling' solution, with a drier surface causing an increase in resistance between the hydrogel and the electrode, and thus decreasing the ionoprinting effectiveness. This is believed to be the cause of some of the variation in results.

Figure 7b shows that with increasing voltage both the amount of electrons and angle produced increase. However, a threshold voltage is required to produce an angle and electrons, these minimum voltages do not occur at the same voltage. A voltage above 2.5V is required to produce an angle. The angle and electrons produced do not depend linearly on the voltage; this can be explained by the increasing build-up of cations near the surface of the electrode, and the additional time required for the ions to diffuse away from the electrode to create larger angles.

Figure 7c shows that there is a linear relationship between moles of electrons produced and angle produced when the initial ion concentration and conductivity of the hydrogel are the same. The graph shows that a threshold amount of electrons is required to produce an angle of 1.28×10^{-5} moles, this is the required amount of electrons and resultant cations required for the hydrogel to overcome its own weight. The production of iron cations from below 1.28×10^{-5} moles of electrons is visibly detectable by the presence of a green/brown line on the surface of the hydrogel. This trend is not true for samples containing various concentrations of LiCl solution, with more concentration producing higher currents and therefore electrons while not producing larger angles.

Figure 7d shows that despite the current increasing with increasing concentration of lithium chloride the angle produced does not increase, but actually decreases. The additional current is not

Figure 7: Graphs of angle and moles of electrons produced from ionoprinting for various variables.

Variable ionoprinting a) duration (0.5-5 minutes), b) voltage (2.5-10.00 V) and d) lithium chloride stock solution (0.05-1.00 M) If not stated, Duration = 1 minute, Voltage = 5 V and Lithium Chloride = 0.1 M. Error bars \pm standard deviation. d) Relationship between moles of electrons and angle produced for samples swollen in 0.10 M of lithium chloride solution. $R^2 = 0.765$

decreases, with increasing lithium chloride solution. However, it was noted that the amount of hydrogen gas generated at the aluminium hydrogel interface increases, suggesting that the electrolysis of water has increased resulting in the production of oxygen at the iron electrode not visibly detectable due to the lack of water at the surface of the hydrogel iron electrode. If this were to be the case the area surrounding the aluminium electrode would become depleted of hydrogen ions, becoming more basic and the area surrounding the iron electrode increasing in hydrogen ions, becoming more acidic. This effect would result in a curvature opposite to the one being achieved by the ionoprinting. While the E_{cell} of water -1.229V and therefore requires this voltage to occur, the E_{cell} for the iron based system is positive indicating it will happen spontaneously. A small voltage, approximately 40mV can be measured across the hydrogel without any power input. However, this voltage is not enough to produce visible metal cations.

3.7 Ionoprinting to create 3D polygons

The ionoprinting technique was extended beyond the simple shapes created previously [5-6], and used to create 3D regular polygons of a cube, triangle based pyramid and an octahedron with printing angles of greater than 90°, 90° and less than 90°, respectively.

Figure 8: Left: Schematic of a cruciform folding into cube through ionoprinting or non-polar solvent and unfolding in a chelating agent or polar solvent. Right: Photographs of the same process. Hydrogel coloured with red food dye

A cube has been created from a flat cruciform by ionoprinting 5 lines as shown in Figure 8, the lines were printed with vanadium wire of diameter 1.5mm at 10V. The ionoprinted lines were printed until an angle of 90° was achieved, creating the cube. The cube was then unfolded in ethanol and then refolded in water twice, before placing the cube in water and regularly changing the water for 7 days. The ions defused into solution and into the rest of the hydrogel removing the effect of the ionoprinted regions and reforming to the flat cruciform cross-section. The cruciform was able to be reprinted into a cube and the deswelling in ethanol and swelling in water successfully completed again. This shows that the ionoprinting produces two-way actuation when exposed to an appropriate stimuli, and can be reprogrammed for different actuation shapes by removing the printed ions and reprinting.

The other 3D polygons were subjected to similar cycles performed in the same manner and can be seen in their freshly ionoprinted state in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Left: Photograph of a triangle based pyramid ionoprinted from a flat triangle. Right: Photograph of an octahedron ionoprinted from its flat mesh. Hydrogels coloured with fluorescein.

3.8 Ionoprinting into kinetic origami inspired 3D shapes

Origami is the Japanese art of paper folding and can be used to create complex three-dimensional shapes from flat sheets of paper. A subsection of origami is kinetic origami, which are origami shapes that have a dynamic property to them; the most famous is the crane, which flaps its wings when its tail and head are pulled away from each other. The kinetic origami design used to create a dynamic hydrogel is one of alternating mountain and valley folds at 45° degrees from each other extending

from the centre of circle to the edge, in a similar manner to how an umbrella is folded up, see Figure 10.

Figure 10: Left: Photograph of circular virgin hydrogel. **Right:** Photograph of ionoprinted hydrogel into umbrella origami design. Hydrogel coloured with fluorescein.

The hydrogel printed into this design is able to transform from a flat shape into a 3D shape, similarly to the polygons shown earlier. Figure 11 shows the complex shape change undergone from unswollen to swollen from the top and side view. Unlike homogenous hydrogels the area displayed in each direction does not follow the normal trend of expansion, instead contraction is observed from the top view (Figure 11a to 11b) and expansion from the side view (Figure 11c to 11d).

Figure 11: Left: Photographs of “umbrella” swelling in water after deswelling in acetone. A) Top view unswollen. B) Top view swollen. C) Side view unswollen. D) Side view swollen. **Right:** Graph of area of hydrogel from top and side against time

By using multiple ionoprinted lines complex shape changes can be performed with homogenous hydrogels. With clever design ionoprinting can be used to vastly extend the shape change of hydrogels and create anisotropic actuation.

4 CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this work has found that metal cations can be used to successfully trigger ionic crosslinks within a hydrogel; in particular it was observed that tri- and tetra-valent metal ions as being the most effective. The level of crosslinking was not only controlled by the cation but also the cation concentration levels as well, until a saturation point was reached. The cations could be successfully removed using a chelating agent, such as EDTA, to restore full swelling of the hydrogel. Furthermore, the overall swelling of the hydrogel can be controlled by the polarity of the solvent into which it is immersed. The relationship between swelling and polarity was shown to be linear with the range from fully swollen to fully unswollen being achieved.

Ionoprinting effectiveness was improved by increasing print time and voltage and decreasing the salt concentration. These results were used to successfully print a range of three-dimensional shapes from their flat counterparts and were shown to be able to cycle from fold to unfolded either retaining or losing their ionoprinted regions each cycle.

Ionoprinting offers a way to quickly and effectively change the shape of hydrogel through localised ionic crosslinking; the process is both reversible and reprogrammable and offers a wide range of possible applications include soft-robotics, artificial muscle tissue and biosensors.

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